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PLANT DIVERSITY OF AT-BASHI RIVER BASIN IN THE INNER TIAN SHAN AREA OF KYRGYZSTAN IN THE LIGHT OF CONSERVATION STRATEGIES

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Abstract

The uniqueness of Kyrgyzstan's vegetation has led to its recognition as a benchmark for Central Asia. Inner Tian Shan area, occupy the eastern part of the At-Bashi-Kara-Koyun depression. Mountains surrounding the valley reach considerable heights. and is one of the largest areas in the area. The study area is important because of its highly impressive plant diversity and almost all ecosystems of Kyrgyzstan are represented here. Several floristic studies have been carried out however, many of these records have undergone changes in nomenclature as well as phylogeny. Therefore this attempt has been made to sort out the real plant diversity by depurating and updating names and synonyms of the plant diversity of the area. The floristic data published from 1934-2015 has been evaluated. The status or changes in the names of plants, position of synonyms, new combinations have been reviewed and corrections done following the www.theplantlist.org. An updated plant diversity data has been proposed. The total number of vascular plants growing in the At-Bashi river basin is 484 taxa (49 families and 225 genera) being full of high-altitude species. In total, 382 taxa belong to the dicots and 99 taxa to the monocots, only 3 species of gymnosperms exists here. The conservation of biological diversity is, therefore, one of the fundamental and urgent priorities to be followed.

Keywords: Tian Shan, Kyrgyzstan, Plant Diversity, Ecology, Life forms, Conservation.

Introduction

Kyrgyzstan is one of the high-mountainous countries in Central Asia with quite rich, unique, and distinctive plant diversity, because the country is located at the junction of two hot climatic zones of the Earth – temperate and subtropical both Tian Shan and Alai are situated here (Kamelin 2002). These excessive contrasts in the natural environment have allowed the preservation of unique plant species in the country.

Tian Shan and Alai are situated within its borders, listed among the 200 world centers of species diversity. The Republic is in the center of the majestic mountain systems of the Tian Shan and Pamir-Alai. More than 60 percent of the country (199.9 thousand km²) is occupied by excessively dissected mountains with altitudes ranging between 500-7,000 m. Nearly 90 percent of its territory is located at an altitude up to 1,500 m and approximately 40 percent of the area is covered by glaciers, snow, rocks, scree, and high-altitude gravelly deserts.

The nature of the relief determines the altitude zonation of natural ecosystems. Inner Tian Shan is a vast, closed area, with elevations varying between 2000-3500 m asl. It is a mountainous country with natural conditions in many respects resembling Central Asia. Remote and hard-to-reach areas are the most important refuges for biodiversity. In terms of climatic features, Inner Tian Shan is very diverse due to differences in relief. The At-Bashi valley together with Inner Tien-

Shan are characterized by serozemic high-mountain desert soils predominantly supporting a xerophytic vegetation (Imanberdieva 2015).

The area is studied with 4,100 species of identified vascular plants belonging to 870 genera and 140 families (Kamelin 2002). Out of these a total of 484 species have been recorded up to now in the “Flora of At-Bashi river basin”, which is 8.8 percent of the flora of Central Asia, 11.8 percent of the flora of Kyrgyzstan. An important characteristic of the floral structure is the ratio of taxa or floristic spectrum (Kamelin 2002).

Vegetation studies have been carried out in its various parts and directions. Sovetkina (1930) is among one of the first researchers who worked on the local vegetation in the At-Bashinskaya basin. Her findings reveal that the valley floor between 2000-2400 m asl is occupied by steppes, stressing a transition of steppe formations. In 1956 Vyhodsev followed her and identified vegetation belts, presenting details on the steppe pastures of the area. Golovkova in 1959 studied the vegetation here and mentions that geobotanical zoning covers almost entire territory of Inner Tien-Shan, including the At-Bashi–Kara-Koyun Valley and the At-Bashi ridge. The authors too refer to the At-Bashi Valley as the largest valleys of Inner Tien-Shan. Shihotov (1974) has investigated the distribution of steppe pastures and reports the predominance of *Stipa capillata* and *S. kir-*

ghisorum, *Artemisia tianschanica* and *Festuca valesiaca*. The flora of the Sary-Goo tract of the At-Bashi Valley has been evaluated lately by Imanberdieva and Lebedeva (2009), reporting 222 species of higher plants belonging to 130 genera and 35 families from the area.

Our aim in this study was to update the data on the plant diversity and ecology of the high-altitude valley of the At-Bashi River basin as it was a must for the future conservation application keeping in view the upcoming climatic scenarios.

Material and Methods

Inner Tien-Shan area is situated at an altitude varying between 2000-3500 m, and the natural conditions in many ways resemble Central Asia (Murzaev 1968) (Figure 1). Climate of the investigated area is very diverse due to differences in terrain, the amount of winter precipitation decreasing towards the east (Academy of Sciences of Kyrgyzstan, 1965).

Several floristic studies have been carried out at the area by Komarov (1934-1969), Shishkin (1950-1965), Vyhodsev (1967), Cherepanov (1995), Ionov et al. (2013) and Imanberdieva (2015), however, many of these records have undergone changes in nomenclature as well as phylogeny. Therefore, this attempt has been made to sort out the real plant diversity of the area by depurating and updating names and synonyms. The floristic data published from 1934-2020 has been evaluated. The status or changes in the names of plants, position of synonyms, new combinations have been reviewed and corrections done following the www.theplantlist.org. An updated plant diversity data has been proposed.

Results and Discussion

The main pattern of distribution of different soil types in general is vertical zonation, which can be traced, starting from the lowest part of the depression to the upper valleys and mountain slopes. Following types and subtypes of soils has been compiled from the studied area (Openlender 1961; Mamytov 1963).

Brown Desert-Steppe Soils: These occupy the lowest and warmest flat part of the At-Bashinsky depression and up the valley of At-Bashi River reaching up to 2,250 m asl. The virgin areas are covered by *Stipa caucasica*, *Artemisia fulvella* and *Achnatherum splendens* steppe communities. In the high-altitudes these are characterized by low biogenicity and the most numerous group of microorganisms is formed by ammonifiers (Obozov 1962) but Actinomycetes also play a significant role in the soil formation.

Chestnut Soils: Distributed above light brown soils, at altitudes between 2,250-2,750 m. The light chestnut soils of the valley contain 3-4 percent humus in the upper horizon with a gradual decrease towards the bottom, soils showing a heavy loam in texture. The vegetation cover includes medium-mountain turf-grass and grass-turf-grass steppes with dominance of *Festuca valesiaca*. In At-Bashi River basin area light chestnut soils are not saline, the reason being availability of water sources for irrigation. Light chestnut saline soils and saline soils are common in the Kara-Koyun Valley, within the basin of At-Bashi river, concentrated in the Sary-Goo tract. Chestnut soils occupy some places within the At-Bashi River basin.

Mountain-valley Dark Chestnut Soils: These occur within the At-Bashi River basin from the village of Ak-Muz to the Bosogo gorge, along the foothills of the ridges – Naryn-Too, Kara-Too, Baybiche-Too and At-Bashy. All these are characterized by a high content of humus but are not saline.

Mountain Chernozems: Distributed on the northern slopes of the At-Bashi ridge, in the form of a narrow strip below the spruce forest between 2,500-2,700 m, occupying the forest clearings up to 2,900 m asl. These are also found in separate spots along deep hollows on the southern slopes of the eastern part of the Naryn-Too ridge. The humus content in mountain chernozems lies between 10.6-14.0 percent in the upper horizon, decreasing by about 50 percent in the second horizon, but decreases gradually with depth. Vegetation is formed by high - grass meadows dominated by *Dactylis glomerata*.

Mountain-Forest Dark Soils: These are distributed on the northern slopes of the eastern half of the At-Bashi ridge and are found in small spots in the shaded gorges of the southern slopes of the Naryn-Too ridge as well, between 2,700-3,100 m. altitudes. The relief is medium-mountainous, usually strongly dissected. The humus content varies within largely, depending on the capacity of soil. The soil surface contains from 7 - 21 percent humus, but as depth increases the amount decreases sharply. Vegetation is formed by *Picea schrenkiana* forests.

Meadow Soils: Commonly found on floodplain river terraces, rich in moisture during flooding.

Mountain Meadow-Steppe Subalpine Soils: These are found in the upper part of the At-Bashi valley, above the Bosogo Gorge, on the southern slopes of the Naryn-Too ridge at an altitude varying between 2,800 (2,900) to 3,200 (3,300) m asl. The percentage of humus is around 9 in the upper horizon but gradually decreases with depth. The vegetation is formed by cryophytic turf-grass steppes with a dominance of *Helictotrichon desertorum*.

Mountain-Meadow Chernozem-like Subalpine Soils: Generally distributed on the northern slopes of the At-Bashi ridge in its eastern half, occurring in separate spots along the shaded exposures of the southern slopes of the Naryn-Too ridge. These are located above spruce forests, at an altitude of 3,000-3,300 m asl. The humus content is high, varying between 16-19 percent in the upper horizon but decreasing with depth. The vegetation is formed by cryophytic medium - grass subalpine meadows dominated by *Phlomis oreophila*.

Mountain-Meadow Alpine Soils: These occur on the northern slopes of the At-Bashi ridge between 2,800-3,300 m, on the southern slopes of the Baybiche-Too ridge and an intermittent belt on the southern slopes of the Naryn-Too ridge between 3,400-3,700 m. The humus content is about 12 percent dominated by cryophytic low-grass (alpine) *Kobresia capilliformis* meadows.

Alluvial Meadow-Forest Soils of Tugai Forests and Shrubs: Common in the floodplain area of the At-Bashi River, on low-power river sediments. The forest here is composed of *Populus afghanica*, *Salix argyræa*, and *Hippophae rhamnoides*.

The soils of the plains and foothills are characterized by relatively low humus content (2-5 %), high carbonate content, with an alkaline reaction of the soil solution. Salinity is widespread and type of salinization is mainly chloride-sulfate by anions and calcium-sodium by cations.

The soils of mountain slopes are characterized by high humus content (6-15 to 20 %), with weak and medium leaching from carbonates, showing neutral or slightly alkaline reaction, lacking the signs of salinization and alkalization.

Salt marshes in the At-Bashi River basin are found on the foothill plains. The process of salt accumulation in soils occurs in the presence of powerful pebble deposits at a shallow depth, with deep groundwater occurrence.

A total of 484 species have been recorded until now in the "Flora of At-Bashi river basin", which is 8.8 percent of the flora of Central Asia, 11.8 percent of the flora of Kyrgyzstan. An important characteristic of the floral structure is the ratio of taxa or floristic spectrum (Kamelin 2002).

Main floral elements of the At-Bashi river basin are angiosperms, represented by 481 species (99.4 %), out of which 382 species (78.9 %) are dicotyledonous plants (Table 3). The ratio of monocotyledonous taxa to dicotyledonous are around 1: 4; the reason being a tendency towards an increasing role of dicotyledons as stressed by Kamelin (2002) as well. Out of the 49 families, the dominant ones in terms of the number of species are: Asteraceae (84 species), Poaceae (60 species) followed by Fabaceae (40 species) (Table 4). The numbers of species in other families are: Lamiaceae (28), Rosaceae (26), Brassicaceae and Ranunculaceae (24 each). These seven families are represented by a total of 286 species, which is 59.09 percent of the flora. The families Cyperaceae, Boraginaceae, Caryophyllaceae, Apiaceae, Salicaceae, Polygonaceae, Chenopodiaceae, Scrophulariaceae, Alliaceae, Gentianaceae, Geraniaceae, Rubiaceae, Plantaginaceae, Liliaceae and Onagraceae are represented by 18, 17, 15, 13, 13, 12, 10, 9, 8, 7, 7, 6, 5, 4, and 4 species respectively.

The 10 monotypic families are: Asparagaceae, Betulaceae, Crassulaceae, Hypericaceae, Limoniaceae, Pinaceae, Polygalaceae, Typhaceae, Thymelaeaceae, and Valerianaceae. The features of the Mediterranean flora are observed in Asteraceae together with a high number of species in Fabaceae and Poaceae. These three families account for about 38 percent of the species composition. The important role of Lamiaceae, Brassicaceae, Rosaceae, and Ranunculaceae is also visible. The families like Cyperaceae, Boraginaceae, Apiaceae, Caryophyllaceae, Salicaceae also are well represented. In terms of the sequence of leading families, Kyrgyzstan flora cannot be classified as Arctic. Its flora reveals a high number of species of Asteraceae, Poaceae, Fabaceae, Lamiaceae, Rosaceae, Brassicaceae, and Ranunculaceae. These play a prominent role in the plant diversity and are thus included among the top ten (Table 5). Cyperaceae family occupies the middle level. We have noted its closeness to the boreal flora. The predominance of the Asteraceae, high abundance of Fabaceae and Poaceae families together with

Apiaceae, Lamiaceae, Brassicaceae, Caryophyllaceae and Salicaceae families indicates typical Mediterranean features of our study area.

The distribution of species based on genera is presented in table 6. The number of genera with largest number of species is 225 (5 to 19 per family). These can be listed as; *Artemisia*- 19, *Carex*- 16, *Astragalus*, *Poa*, *Salix*- 9 species each. *Allium*, *Oxytropis* and *Potentilla* - 8 species each, *Gentiana* - 7 species, *Ligularia*, *Ranunculus*, *Rosa* - 6 species each, *Galium*, *Geranium*, *Festuca*, *Erigeron*, *Saussurea* and *Stipa* - 5 species each. These genera make up 29.1 percent of the total flora. Many species belong to the genera with a small number of species (2-9). Monotypic genera in the area are 10 (2.1 % of the total flora). The polymorphism of the genera *Potentilla*, *Artemisia*, *Poa*, and *Carex* indicates boreal features of the flora. Annuals are distributed mainly in the areas under anthropogenic impacts. The analysis of the generic spectrum confirms the family composition and indicates the intermediate nature of the flora in the study area.

Analysis of Life Forms

The woody vegetation includes trees, shrubs, and semi-woody shrubs. The herbaceous plants include perennials, annuals, and biennials (Table 7). Trees, shrubs, and semi-shrubs are represented by 50 species (10.3 % of the total flora). *Picea schrenkiana* and *Juniperus turkestanica* are the dominants of special types of vegetation - reforested from *Picea* and *Juniperus*. The valleys are dominated by *Sorbus tianschanica*; alongside the rivers are common the genera like *Betula* and *Salix*. Shrubs are dominated by such genera as; *Caragana*, *Rosa*, *Spirea*, *Tamarix*, and few others. Communities with shrub species of junipers are formed on the slopes of southern and close exposures, in the subalpine belt.

Woody plants in the flora are rather poor, both in life forms and in species composition. They have important phytocenotic significance because these form special communities. There are few semi-woody plants (17 species- 3.5 %) confined to dry habitats. Herbaceous plants constitute the absolute majority in the flora with a representation of 417 (86.2 %), most being weeds distributed on the roadsides, alongside the trails, old cattle camps and on the slopes of the southern exposures. Due to the moisture deficit in summer, there is a significant number of bulbous polycarpics (8 species-1.7 %) and other life forms with storage organs that serve to survive unfavorable season.

The problems faced by the biodiversity are among the priority issues in the biology and ecology of the past, present and future. The key to safeguard it lies in the search for ways to overcome the ecological crisis. Threats to some plant species in their natural habitats include many adverse activities like; expansion of agricultural fields, excessive deforestation for fuel, and uncontrolled grazing (Imanberdieva et al. 2018a).

According to the plant species composition together with the rare species, Inner Tian Shan shows good connection with the flora of the eastern part of the Alai Range and the Eastern Pamirs. So far, no floral inventory has been carried out in Kyrgyzstan, as well as in the At-Bashi Valley. In order to restore and maintain biological diversity and protect vegetation cover, it is

necessary to protect not individual plant species that are threatened with extinction, but communities with a larger number of species and their natural ecological habitats together with the multiplicity of use of natural forage lands, expansion in the network of specially protected natural territories- nature reserves, national parks and the organization of an environmental monitoring system.

Climate change may have a direct and indirect influence on a country's economy by reducing the availability of desirable species of flora and fauna at higher altitudes and transferring key species from lower to higher regions. In many circumstances, the dominance of migrating species will displace more native species, lowering the value and productivity of these economically valued species (Anup and Ghimire 2015). A temperature increase of one-degree Celsius changes the permanent line of tree in higher altitude by approximately 150 meters, which was already seen in the Himalayas in western Nepal (Gupta 2010).

The study of economically important plant species, especially their biological characteristics during the current climate change scenarios which include natural disasters like drought, floods, and erosion are topics of great interest. These are very important because it will help in managing the viability of ecosystems and land resources. Latest trend in demand in the country is to produce organic foods and save the biodiversity (Ozturk et al. 2017a). Currently the nature and intensity of floods, heavy rains, and drought are changing the environment in the area drastically. As a result of these changes individual species and their habitats are seriously destroyed. Any changes in the water regime or

other abiotic factors leads to disturbances in the distribution and abundance of endangered species and ecosystems, followed by an increase in the overall loss of biodiversity (Rannow et al. 2014).

The integration of all living things, together with their ecology, habitat, and functional connection, is biodiversity, which is threatened by climate change and has a negative impact on tourism and other forms of revenue. (Anup, et al. 2019).

The bulbous plants and wild flowers have a great commercial value. However, their overharvesting together with other wild plants has led to a rapid disappearance of many plant taxa. Many people among the population in the country have developed a very bad habit of picking wild flowers during spring and summer seasons. This destructive activity is proving highly detrimental for the plants. Some of the plants collected are rare or endangered (Imanberdieva et al. 2018b). The wild growing plants of the genera: *Allium*, *Aster*, *Campanula*, *Gagea*, *Gentiana*, *Iris*, *Primula*, *Trollius*, and *Tulipa* are affected highly by such collections. There are several economically important decorative plants. It is necessary to note that the species of trees and shrub are used in the urban and rural house gardens: *Betula tianschanica*, *Picea schrenkiana*, *Sorbus tianschanica* together with the species of genera *Rosa*, and *Salix*.

Statements and Declarations

The authors whose names are listed immediately below certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity. No funding was received to assist with the preparation of this manuscript. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Tables and Figures

Table 1. Average monthly air temperature (°C) over the years of research 2009-2016 years. (According to the At-Bashi agrometeorological post (abs. height. 2400 m above sea level)).

Year	MONTHS												Average annual	During the growing season
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII		
2009	-19.2	-13.0	-3.3	6.7	10.5	25.6	14.8	13.3	10.7	5.8	-3.7	-13.7	11.7	13.6
2010	-15.4	-12.2	-3.2	6.4	11.5	14.5	15.8	16.1	10.2	5.1	-0.4	-12.6	10.2	12.4
2011	-16.2	-8.3	-1.7	6.7	12.5	14.0	16.7	16.1	11.8	6.1	-2.2	-14.5	10.6	13.0
2012	-21.0	-14.7	-5.8	8.8	12.5	14.6	17.9	16.2	11.4	3.8	-2.6	-13.8	11.9	14.0
2013	-17.8	-13.5	1.4	7.9	11.2	15.0	16.5	15.7	11.8	6.0	-5.4	-11.5	11.1	13.0
2014	-14.0	-14.6	-2.8	6.2	12.5	14.2	17.2	14.9	11.5	5.2	-4.5	-17.6	11.3	13.0
2015	-15.3	-9.8	-3.1	6.9	11.8	14.4	19.7	15.5	10.3	5.8	-1.0	-15.4	10.8	13.1
2016	-16.0	-14.9	1.2	7.5	11.1	15.0	15.6	15.0	12.6	3.1	-3.9	-12.7	10.7	12.8

Table 2.

Precipitation (mm) during 2009-2016. (from At-Bashi Agrometeorology Station (Altitude. 2400 m above sea level)).

Years	MONTHS												Σ per year	Σ during the growing season
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII		
2009	3.0	6.6	5.4	62.0	45.0	50.3	54.5	44.6	28.4	7.7	10.1	4.8	322.4	284.8
2010	23.1	42.0	30.1	15.7	55.5	54.1	33.6	34.1	70.9	28.4	0.6	6.3	394.4	263.9
2011	2.5	26.4	17.8	34.6	51.0	64.8	21.1	18.1	11.2	28.2	39.6	5.9	321.2	200.8
2012	2.9	7.6	25.7	46.8	56.2	50.9	14.2	14.6	36.2	13.6	10.9	3.7	283.3	218.9
2013	10.5	22.6	13.9	45.3	64.3	39.3	33.2	57.0	3.7	3.2	4.9	3.8	301.7	242.8
2014	2.2	6.4	10.2	16.2	11.9	47.9	3.6	8.6	8.2	43.2	38.3	1.7	198.4	96.4
2015	5.2	14.3	20.8	27.0	63.8	92.6	21.4	30.9	12.2	16.1	17.0	23.5	344.8	247.9
2016	5.6	4.6	13.2	61.6	120.4	97.7	69.3	10.4	9.4	26.2	19.8	33.4	471.6	368.8

Table 3.

Plant Diversity in the At-Bashi river basin.				
	Gymnospermae	Angiospermae		Total number
		Dicotyledoneae	Monocotyledoneae	
Family	2	38	9	49
Genera	2	187	36	225
Taxa	3	382	99	484

Table 4.

Families	Genera		Species	
	number	% of the total	number	% of the total
Aceraceae	1	0.4	2	0.4
Alliaceae	1	0.4	8	1.7
Apiaceae	11	4.8	13	2.7
Asparagaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
Asteraceae	31	13.7	84	17.4
Berberidaceae	1	0.4	2	0.4
Betulaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
Boraginaceae	11	4.8	17	3.5
Brassicaceae	16	7.0	24	5.0
Campanulaceae	2	0.8	2	0.4
Caprifoliaceae	1	0.4	2	0.4
Caryophyllaceae	8	3.5	15	3.1
Chenopodiaceae	7	3.1	10	2.1
Convolvulaceae	1	0.4	2	0.4
Cupressaceae	1	0.4	2	0.4
Crassulaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
Cyperaceae	2	0.8	18	3.7
Dipsacaceae	1	0.4	2	0.4
Elaeagnaceae	2	0.8	2	0.4
Ephedraceae	1	0.4	3	0.6
Fabaceae	13	5.7	40	8.3
Gentianaceae	1	0.4	7	1.4
Geraniaceae	3	1.3	7	1.4
Hypericaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
<u>Iridaceae</u>	1	0.4	3	0.6
<i>Juncaceae</i>	1	0.4	2	0.4
Lamiaceae	15	6.6	28	5.8
Liliaceae	2	0.8	4	0.8
Limoniaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
Linaceae	1	0.4	3	0.6
Onagraceae	2	0.8	4	0.8
Orchidaceae	1	0.4	2	0.4
Papaveraceae	2	0.8	2	0.4
Parnasiaceae	2	0.8	3	0.6
Pinaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
Plantaginaceae	2	0.8	5	1.0
Poaceae	26	11.5	60	12.4
Polygonaceae	6	2.6	12	2.5
Polygalaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
Primulaceae	3	1.3	3	0.6
Ranunculaceae	13	5.7	24	5.0
Rosaceae	11	4.8	26	5.4
Rubiaceae	2	0.8	6	1.2
Salicaceae	2	0.8	13	2.7
Scrophulariaceae	6	2.6	9	1.9
Tamaricaceae	2	0.8	3	0.6
Typhaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
Thymelaeaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
Valerianaceae	1	0.4	1	0.2
Total	225	100	484	100

Table 5.

Dominant families in the At-Bashi river basin			
	Family	Number of genera	Number of species
1	Asteraceae	31	84
2	Poaceae	26	60
3	Fabaceae	13	40
4	Lamiaceae	15	28
5	Rosaceae	11	26
6	Brassicaceae	16	24
7	Ranunculaceae	13	24
8	Cyperaceae	2	18
9	Boraginaceae	11	17
10	Caryophyllaceae	8	15
11	Apiaceae	11	13
12	Salicaceae	2	13
	TOTAL	159	362

Table 6.

Dominant Genera in the Flora of At-Bashi River Basin		
Genera	Number of species	% of the total composition
<i>Artemisia</i>	19	13.5
<i>Carex</i>	16	11.3
<i>Astragalus</i>	9	6.4
<i>Poa</i>	9	6.4
<i>Salix</i>	9	6.4
<i>Allium</i>	8	5.7
<i>Oxytropis</i>	8	5.7
<i>Potentilla</i>	8	5.7
<i>Gentiana</i>	7	5.0
<i>Ligularia</i>	6	4.3
<i>Ranunculus</i>	6	4.3
<i>Rosa</i>	6	4.3
<i>Galium</i>	5	3.5
<i>Geranium</i>	5	3.5
<i>Festuca</i>	5	3.5
<i>Erigeron</i>	5	3.5
<i>Saussurea</i>	5	3.5
<i>Stipa</i>	5	3.5
TOTAL:	141	100

Table 7.

Life form spectrum of the At-Bashi river basin		
Life form	Number of Genera	% of the Flora
Woody plants		
Tree	15	3.1
Shrub	33	6.8
Small Shrubs	2	0.4
Semi-woody plants		
Half-shrub half-shrub	17	3.5
Ground Level Herbs		
Perennials	336	69.4
Biennials	11	2.3
Ephemera	70	14.5
Total	484	100

Fig. 1. Geographical Location of At-Bashi Valley of the Inner Tien-Shan of Kyrgyzstan

Fig.2. Average monthly air temperature (°C) and the amount of precipitation (mm) covering the period from 2009 to 2016.

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